

SMARANDACHE COUNTER-PROJECTIVE GEOMETRY

by

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Abstract:

All three axioms of the projective geometry are denied in this new geometry.

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Introduction:

This type of geometry has been constructed by F.Smarandache[4] in 1969.

Let P, L be two sets, and r a relation included in $P \times L$. The elements of P are called points, and those of L lines. When (p, l) belongs to r , we say that the line l contains the point p .

For these, one imposes the following COUNTER-AXIOMS:

- (I) There exist: either at least two lines, or no line, that contains two given distinct points.
- (II) Let p_1, p_2, p_3 be three non-collinear points, and q_1, q_2 two distinct points. Suppose that $\{p_1, q_1, p_3\}$ and $\{p_2, q_2, p_3\}$ are collinear triples. Then the line containing p_1, p_2 , and the line containing q_1, q_2 do not intersect.
- (III) Every line contains at most two distinct points.

We consider that in a discontinuous space one can construct a model to this geometry.

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